

Significance of Yoga for Working Women's Mental and Spiritual Health

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Abstract— In daily life yoga is a system of practice that has eight limbs, levels or degrees of development for a holistic health. It seems that the mental health is clear and control than the physically and spiritually health is also sign positive nature. When you are fit and perfectly healthy you can feel your inner-self and your surrounding area's level go for spiritual health. Yoga is an Ancient and traditional ways of living for Indians where so many methods and attitudes are involve which attain to higher level of consciousness and create different outlook like balanced between body, mind and soul, positivity to help others, connect much deeper in psychologically, respect for all and so many. Yoga word is originates from "Sanskrit" literature which means "to unite". In modern era life is becoming very fast and hazardous because every person wants to win and achieving everything. Due to this developing technology different diseases, disorder, and others unbalanced issues are arising. Behind that the person is forgetting that what the meaning of life, what is the definition of health and the priorities in life? Nowadays people doing yoga but not for healthy lifestyle but just for some cure like stress, anxiety, back pain, arthritis and many more health conditions. In our country women are equals to men in every field but still they are facing more inside and outside problems as compare to men. Women are affecting by several in physical health issues like obesity, irregular menstrual, PCOD, PCOS, interstitial cystitis, pregnancy issues, breast cancer, diabetes, and in mental problems schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, isolation, Depression and so on. To do each of her parts flawlessly, elegantly, dutiful and with limit. It is crucial for women to preserve good and holistic health in their lifestyle. Yoga is a way by that they can achieve all of these and live with peacefully. Yoga is an art of life and science of living with divinity. For decades in yoga has many research but here author just wants to tell that how more important yoga for a working women's life.

Keywords: Yoga, Mental health, Spiritual health, Working Women.

I. INTRODUCTION

21st century is going rapidly with technology where the readily and instant solution for all problems exists and it is acceptable. Every person is living with confliction and wants instant result. Women are the most important play a role for a family, for a society and for a nation. Today men and women are almost equal in every field, but in somewhere women are generally feel failure, uncomfortable, and zero in action. The reason is poor health. At the age of after 30-40 women's status about the wellness is very low and the holistic philosophy comes down.

So the yoga practices make them individually supreme and realization of mind's activities. The goal of yoga is to develop strategies for enhancing mental and spiritual focus.

II. WOMEN'S STATUS IN INDIA

Women have more responsible for bearing children, fulfill their all needs and requirements, yet they suffer malnourished and in deficient. From morning to night the whole day women are as usual overworked and finalize to complete all of domestic chores. India's constitution says that women have equal rights to men despite that most of the Indian women are uneducated, powerless, and if some are educated but still they are unemployed just because of family's under pressure. Even government and constitution try to make more schemes for girl's education but only few female around 39% attend the primary education. Behind that so many causes like education for daughter is useless, early marriage, household responsibility, gender discrimination, poverty, lack of support, poor environment, in any rural region many health issues seems, violence, and etc. According to the "UN human development report (1996)" In India approximately 65% women are illiterate. Nation Crime Record Bureau (1994) of India's Government data says that here is the most violence against women she is victim of domestic violence, sexual violence (35%), family violence, community and work place violence, high infant mortality violence and to be continuing...

Family is frequently or usually equivalent with shelter where every person bring off love, care, attention, safety, security, comfort zone, own rights and many more but the review and research, evidence suggested that it is also a location where lives are endangered and where some of the most severe types of violence happen against women and girls are fostered. Mostly domestic violence are carry out by males who have a power of family or intimacy he can be father, brother, uncle, boyfriend, husband, father-in-law, sons or other relative. In India approx 70% of women are victim of domestic violence in every year. In other crime women face violence include forced pregnancy, abortion, infanticide, dowry, early marriage etc. Domestic Violence is mainly classified under the following abusing:

- **PHYSICALLY:** Abusing is one of the most affected causes under the violence. In physical abuse involve feelings of intimidation, pain, injury, or other outer body suffering harm. Based on data of (OVW) office of violence Against Women, 41.31 percent of women are reported physical abuse.
- **SEXUALLY:** Any circumstance in which force or fear is used to coerce participation in unwanted sexual behavior is considered sexual abuse. Even if the victim is a spouse or other intimate partner with whom consensual sex has already occurred, forcing someone to have sex against their will constitutes an act of hostility and violence.
- **MENTALLY:** It is also known as emotional or psychological abuse where mortify the victim publicly or privately, overall controlling what the victim can do cannot, victim makes to feel embarrassed, isolating from family, friends and close person, express the dependency, and denying for their needs, requirements, and basic sources.
- **VERBALLY:** According to a conducting survey, it is a form of abusing behaviour with the help of language or unnecessary words. It is a obscenity where a person do abnormal behaviour and its accounts for nearly 81 percent.
- **ECONOMICALLY:** It is totally depend on victim's money and other incoming sources. Here is included the victim which are finishing education, acquiring job or employment, and for some other issues. It is common for the victim to accept less money as the abuse continues.

These types of so many causes are affect our society, where the women's said to be "goddess" and the crime and violence are happening daily and women are making victim for all of these. That is why women are suffering from the all issues and disorders. From the birth to death, morning to night, daughter to mother, family to society and inside to outside she overworked not for self or own happiness but for others, and that others are doing shameless thing. She become more pessimistic, discouraging, hesitating, hopelessness, and very negative towards their own life. These all things are hollowing women to inside by mentally or spiritually.

III. MENTAL & SPIRITUAL HEALTH

According to WHO- "A state of complete physical, mental, spiritual, and social well-being is called Health". Now a day every person wants to live fit and healthy and they lives but if we talk about the mental and spiritual health we see that most of the people are suffering from mentally and spiritually. Especially women who are engaged with all works and they don't have time for own. In generally life is going led by the mental and inner peace rather than having all under control and pressure but women are. The dimension of health; physical, mental, spiritual and social all are connected to each other. For the perfect and healthy life they should be balance.

MENTAL HEALTH: For the overall personality development two most important aspects are mandatory one is power of imagination creativity and second is will power. They both are the part of arts and technology. Mental health is the root causes for all illness it means the capability to live congenially with one-self and others. A person has some good mental qualities are:

Comfertable with enviornment/ Society
Self-Respect
Knows well about their limitations and capabilities
Able to control emotions
Accepts both situation; success and failiure equally
Enjoy the company of people
Capable of leading a group as a leader
Readily accepts responsibility
Potential of making own decisions
Making the realistic goal of life

Women are untouched for these all qualities and it makes them unhealthy by mentally. Gradually so many psychological disorders are generate and their life make hell and spoil. Hesitation, shy nature, inferiority, low confidence, insecure, helplessness, dependency and so many causes affect their mental status. Working women mostly survive from psychological and abnormal behavior issues because the conscious and subconscious mind unable to reach experiences and feelings. Therefore, in many cases women commit suicide. Most of the time happiness is shaken by minor disturbances and emotionally they get feel lack of support and perceived negativity from the all side. In rural region women's condition are very poor and discriminatory. The women's socio-economic status of the society they were engaged in more hazardous labor work than men. In the form of gender biased their society is men stream society. Unfortunately, our developing country is unable to find out them from that situation and implement many movement and campaign favor of women like women empowerment and so on. In urban area if

women are employed or working any sector that does not mean there women are free from unlimited worries. They feel more insecure about the society, about the family, about the working place. The only difference between rural and urban women is economic independency. Mentally they feel more depressed and stressed. They see family, household works, office work, social works and all. Still they faced many disorders and issues because they don't have time for self.

SPIRITUAL HEALTH: The principal and main goal of spiritual health is “Ahimsa Paramo Dharam:” The meaning of this statement is in thoughts, in words, in feelings and in action we should be non-violence. The way to achieve spiritual health is prayer, meditation, peace, mantra chant, positive thinking, and awareness and it is totally depend on mental health status. If you are mentally fit your spiritual health work automatically. The spiritual dimension is “concern itself with the inner world which we called peace of self realization” where the tendency towards laxity, the source of intelligent, and the emotional foundation. It is a journey of inward, where the layer of subtle body and mind unfold themselves and personality opened instinctively. Mostly women are not aware of the spiritual health. It creates a perfect balanced between physical, psychological and social aspects of human life. Here is possible to approach spirituality from a psychological, philosophical, transcendental-religious and phenomenological perspective. Spirituality is a broad and nebulous concept. (Piedmont and Leach, 2002). Spirituality makes a person more optimistic, positive, aware of sense, comfort, social-contributed, and empathetic. Most of the people choose spirituality through the music, art, nature, meditation, yoga, etc. everyone has their own value and principal. At the end spirituality learned the purpose of life. That's why it is to be said that in the early stages of life everyone should be balanced these three dynamics of spirituality:

IV. YOGA

Yoga is spreading with rapidly in the world for every age group. For the sick it is medicine, for the restless mind it is it gives peace, for the youth it becomes craziness, for the common person it is becoming fashion and trend to be fit and more attractive, for the old-age it is developing memory and desire to live and for the childhood it makes creativity like body posture.

Yoga has multifold advantages. Not only in India but the whole world yoga is becoming popular. Now a day it is becoming a part of education and management. Doctors, psychologist and many Specialists use it to reveal deeper awareness layers as they strive for perfections. The contemporary medical system has largely supplanted the traditional medical system throughout the world due to its rational foundation. It has proven to be extremely successful in protecting people from the deadly effects of infectious and communicable diseases. In the every field, every area, yoga is significantly advancing the field of modern medicine.

In the traditional terminology yoga is given by our ancient which is helps to joining of jivatma to parmatma, individual to universal, outside to inside, dark to light, egoistic to blissful and artificial to natural. According to our saint yoga is a systematic conscious process of gaining control over the mind and body. Yoga helps in growth entirely and learns to maintain the level of mind state. The yoga English word is come from Sanskrit language “yuj” which means “union”. Yoga is a discipline to achieve a union harmony of universal consciousness. Holistically, yoga is a best cure remedy for all to gain physical, mental, spiritual, and social well-being. Every person wish to live in harmony with oneseft to others but in this technology era result is opposite more and more people are suffer from mental tension and could not achieve spiritual life. Insomnia, stress, over-thinking and other psychological disorder are generating in every age of person. Heart-attack, Diabetes, Migraine, and Cancer like dangerous diseases are happening at the early ages just because of unhealthy mental status. This is why to be said that in daily life yoga must be included for balanced harmony. As follows yoga aids us in coping with each day demands, issues and worries. On the

other hand in spirituality, yoga gives on to supreme awareness and realization with the delightful in the union of individual to universe. At the emotional level of yoga is a state of stability; at the level of mental state equilibrium between congregation and detachment, and equanimity at the physical or body level. Hence, yoga is very states of higher, subtler layer of mind.

V. THE FOUR BRANCHES OF YOGA

In the world every person has different thinking, nature, behavior, and environment so to bring out the transformation in yoga mainly four branches are help to reach out their well holistic health. Women can create their new journey about to health, life, and to own. Day by day yoga practices make them comfortable and trying to solve problems, unhappiness, negativity, mentally upsets, reduce tension, hyperactivity etc.. Yoga is a process of all around development also a powerful tool to manifest hidden potential energy. In Vedas first yoga techniques were written, where a collection of texts which promotes healthy and wealthy with ritual emphasis. After many years sage “Patanjali” written this texts in sutras form which we known as “Patanjali Yoga Sutra”.

VI. EMPIRICAL STUDIES ON YOGA

In modern era yoga become multidimensional which goal to improve health and holistic wellness. It seems that yoga empirical is using for treatment, therapy, prevention, and clinically for cure. Originally yoga was supported for spiritually growth. The principal and practices of yoga improved many diseases. Here is some research based on yoga:

- ✓ Gallagher, et.al showed that yoga practices can reduce anxiety and depression among high-risk pregnant women. (2020)
- ✓ Lu et al find their study that yoga decreased stress and improved sleep quality among menopausal women. (2020).
- ✓ Alleva, et al analyzed that practice of hath yoga affect positively by lower objection and high embodiment among adult women. (2020).
- ✓ Bhole M.V, Karambelkar suggest that there have yoga produces different acute physiological changes. (1969).
- ✓ Prabha,V saw the positive effect of SKY simple kundalini yoga on self confidence among women who were suffering from menstrual problem. (2016).
- ✓ Yadav S.K et.al explained the importance of yoga in daily life, where pranayam, ashtanga yoga, and meditation were included. (2015).
- ✓ Maheswarananda, Find out that how important yoga in daily life. This study happened in European Universities. (2000).
- ✓ Muthuswami, assessed that daily yoga practice made women internally strong and cured from anaemia disease. (2013).
- ✓ Sivananda, S. said that the help of yoga can achieve everything in the life for divinity. (1999).
- ✓ Naragatti, S to explore the yoga studies effect on health. (2020).
- ✓ Ray, et.al find that yoga practices makes life more healthy and stabling. (2011)
- ✓ Bhavnani, and Sarang confirmed in the research paper that yoga training bring about the life’s more attention, concentrative and creative. (2007)
- ✓ Chen, K.M et.al said that continue yoga practice plays a greater role in the balanced between physical and mental health. (2010).
- ✓ Senthilvadivu, found the positive effect of yoga on women employee who were suffering from physiological and psychological disorders. (2013).
- ✓ Kumar, K find out in the study that yoga intervention has been shown positive and success result about the mental well-being. (2012).
- ✓ Kumar, K studied that yoga effect a positive impact towards physical and mental health. (2015)
- ✓ Guerra et al found that weekly 30 minute of yoga meditation for 8 weeks improved quality of life and sleep.
- ✓ Chandravadhana, conducted a study on women who were suffering from stress by bio-chemically, psychologically & physiologically and achieve significant or improving result towards the issues. (2013).

VII. CONCLUSION

Since yoga was introduced to the west 100 years ago. It has evolved from an arcane religious ritual to a thriving science of integrating. Yet, there are still many restrictions that prevent yoga from being used more frequently in clinical care. The main

one among them is a lack of knowledge of yoga's science. Yoga could be incorporated into the medical curriculum to solve this issue.

To finalize the fundamental principal of "significance of yoga for working women's mental and spiritual health" is for unity and developing. Spiritually guidance and mentally well aspirants will be capable for realization and connection for God to the way of any path. Well- being, healthy, and free from unlimited worries are in your hand. So everyone should be aware and also do others. Regular yoga practices make a person enlightening and in our society women are already a face of lightening despite of so many issues. Continuing is the best medicine for all cure after that we get achieve goal and success for a healthy and wealthy nation.

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